

A REVIEW OF MONOPOLE ANTENNA FOR ISM BAND APPLICATIONS

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Abstract:

This research delves into advancements in antenna design and their diverse applications, particularly within the ISM (Industrial, Scientific, and Medical) band. Various studies contribute to the development of compact and high-performance antennas, showcasing innovative designs tailored for specific purposes. Examples include a coplanar waveguide fed z-monopole implantable antenna with ISM band communication capabilities, a rectangular monopole antenna demonstrating complete ISM band coverage for potential biomedical applications, and a self-grounding semi-circular gap dual-band flexible antenna designed for wireless body area networks, offering higher gain and efficiency in bent states, ideal for wearable smart terminals. This research extends beyond antenna design, highlighting the role of Optical Coherence Tomography Angiography (OCT-A) in non-invasive imaging of retinal and choroidal microvasculature. This technology, applied to neurodegenerative diseases, facilitates early detection and monitoring of various conditions. This research also explores developments in electronic contact lenses for non-invasive monitoring, featuring a proof-of-concept lens operating in the ISM band with potential applications in health monitoring. The landscape expands into implantable devices, where an electrically small circularly polarized antenna system is introduced for retinal prosthesis, operating in the ISM band. The comprehensive overview emphasizes the diverse approaches and innovations in monopole antenna design, shaping the landscape of wireless communication and healthcare technologies. This project tries to develop a highly efficient and compact monopole antenna is poised to contribute significantly to the seamless operation of wireless communication devices in various industrial, scientific, and medical applications. This project lays the foundation for improved wireless communication technologies, impacting domains ranging from consumer electronics to emerging healthcare solutions.

Key Words: ISM, Monopole, Meta Materials

1.INTRODUCTION

In recent years, advancements in communication technologies have paved the way for the development of diverse wireless applications, ranging from IoT devices to medical implants.

One critical aspect in the implementation of these applications is the design of efficient antennas that cater to specific frequency bands. This project focuses on the meticulous design and optimization of a monopole antenna tailored for the Industrial, Scientific, and Medical (ISM) band, specifically operating in the frequency range of 2.4 to 2.5 GHz.

Significance of ISM Band is allocated globally for unlicensed usage, has become integral in wireless communication systems. Devices operating in this band include Wi-Fi networks, Bluetooth devices, and various industrial applications. Designing an effective monopole antenna for this frequency range is pivotal for ensuring reliable wireless communication in a multitude of contexts. Creating a monopole antenna for the ISM band poses challenges such as achieving optimal impedance matching, radiation efficiency, and minimizing interference.

Moreover, considerations for the compactness, conformity, and flexibility of the antenna are vital, especially in applications where space is constrained or when integrating the antenna into wearable devices.

Investigation and optimization of the dimensions and parameters of a monopole antenna to ensure resonate within the ISM band. Explore techniques for enhancing antenna performance, including gain, directivity, and impedance matching. Evaluate the antenna's conformity to different substrates and assess its compactness, especially concerning wearable applications.

2.LITERATURE REVIEW:

This literature review delves on two sections the first section is about monopole antenna. The section I mainly deals with different types of monopole antenna based on its structure, size and dielectric constant. The section II consists of the different types of ISM band frequency monopole antenna.

SECTION I: MONOPOLE ANTENNA

The landscape of monopole antenna design is characterized by a fascinating array of journals, each contributing to the nuanced exploration of innovative solutions tailored to the diverse challenges and applications within wireless communication systems and ISM applications. [1] stands out with its focus on introducing a circular monopole antenna, heralding potential advancements in wireless communication system performance. The emphasis here is on addressing critical challenges related to gain, bandwidth, and radiation patterns.[2] takes a different approach, proposing a compact design featuring a defected ground plane. This design choice indicates an ambitious aspiration – the attainment of wideband functionality, a pivotal requirement for applications necessitating versatile frequency coverage. The deliberate incorporation of a defected ground plane in this design is a strategic move to enhance the antenna's characteristics, exerting influence over radiation patterns and impedance matching.

[3] delves into the development of a compact monopole antenna with the capability to operate across multiple frequency bands. These include the ISM band, Bluetooth, WiMAX,

and WIFI. The inherent versatility of this design is indispensable for contemporary devices supporting a gamut of wireless standards, thereby demanding efficient coverage across a diverse spectrum of frequencies.[4] adopts an application-specific approach. The monopole antenna is meticulously tailored to cater to the specific needs of wireless energy metering and smart applications. This design is anticipated to optimize factors such as efficiency and size, aligning seamlessly with the unique requirements of applications where reliability and compact form factors are critical. The convergence of machine learning and antenna design takes center stage in [5] Departing from traditional optimization methods, this journal explores the integration of machine learning algorithms to fine-tune the operating parameters of the double T-shaped monopole antenna. This showcases a promising avenue for adaptive and efficient designs, marking a significant departure from conventional optimization strategies.

In the realm of compatibility with multiple communication standards [6] accentuates the need for wideband characteristics. Such attributes are indispensable for the seamless coexistence of multiple wireless communication standards like WIFI, LTE, and WiMax. This design approach directly addresses the escalating demand for uninterrupted connectivity in contemporary devices.[7] introduces an accessible design procedure. This procedure, facilitated by characteristic mode analysis, simplifies the intricate design process, making it more approachable for practitioners and designers alike. Adding an artistic flair to design inspiration, [8] introduces a V- adding an artistic flair to design inspiration, introduces a V-shaped monopole antenna design. This design incorporates a defected ground structure inspired by Chichena Itzia, aiming to achieve ultra-wideband (UWB) performance. This is particularly tailored to applications demanding broad frequency coverage. In a culmination of these diverse approaches, [9] explores the development of a wideband printed monopole antenna. Such a

Figure 4: Linear array of monopole antenna (MPA)

Figure 4: Geometry of circular monopole antenna with ground plane

Figure 4: Monopole antenna with defected ground plane and its iteration

Figure 4: V-shaped monopole antenna with its geometry iteration

design is deemed crucial for supporting high data rate communication in contemporary wireless

networks, where the need for robust connectivity is paramount. The mentioned journals collectively unfold a tapestry of monopole antenna designs. Ranging from circular and compact configurations to application-specific optimizations, machine learning integration, and wideband solutions, the overarching theme is the relentless pursuit of enhanced performance and versatility. Access to the full texts of these journals would undoubtedly provide a deeper understanding of the methodologies and findings, offering a valuable resource for researchers, engineers, and enthusiasts navigating the complex landscape of wireless communication systems.

Table1: Different Types Of Monopole Antenna With Its Dimensions

REFER ENCE No	ANTENNA TYPE	ANTENNA SIZE (Lx W x H) (cu.mm)	DIELECTRIC CONSTANT	OPERATING FREQUENCY (G HZ)
[1]	Circular Monopole	70 x70x 1.6	4.4	F1=2.41
				F2=5.6
[2]	Compact Monopole with Defected Ground Plane	38.92 x 40 x 1.6	4.4	F1=3.91
				F2=6.01
				F3=7.83
[3]	Multiband Monopole	34 x 43x1.6	2.4	F1=1.44
				F2=2.35
				F3=3.45
				F4=4.45
[4]	Printed Monopole	45 x17 x1.6		F1=868MHz
				F2=2.4
[6]	Microstrip Monopole	38 x7 x0.035	4.7	F1=5
[8]	V-Shaped Monopole with Defected Ground Structure	25 x26 x1.6		F1=4.2GHz
[9]	Wideband Printed Monopole	48.32 x43.72 x0.8	2.2	F1=1.45
				F2=2.43

SECTION II: ISM BAND MONOPOLE ANTENNA

The literature in the realm of monopole antennas within the Industrial, Scientific, and Medical (ISM) band at 2.45 GHz unfolds a multifaceted narrative, as revealed by a series of insightful journals. This literature review offers a nuanced exploration of the distinctive facets investigated in each study, illuminating the collective efforts to optimize monopole antennas for diverse applications within the ISM band.

The first foray into this expansive field is encapsulated [10]. Here, the focus sharpens on antennas tailor-made for implantable biomedical devices. The Z-monopole configuration emerges as a key player, offering promise in ensuring robust communication within the 2.45 GHz ISM band—a spectrum often dedicated to medical telemetry. The meticulous analysis and

design considerations underscore the earnest endeavor to seamlessly integrate wireless communication into the intricate landscape of biomedical applications, ultimately advancing the realms of patient monitoring and health care delivery.

Expanding the horizon to accommodate a broader array of applications, [11] introduces an M-shaped printed monopole antenna. This design exhibits versatility by spanning applications such as GPS, ISM, and W-LAN. The deliberate choice of the M-shaped configuration suggests a strategic decision to achieve a wide bandwidth, thereby endowing the antenna with the flexibility to adeptly support diverse communication standards within the ISM band. This adaptability aligns with the contemporary demand for antennas that can seamlessly traverse multiple frequency bands and standards—a crucial attribute in the dynamic landscape of modern wireless communication systems.

[12] takes the spotlight with a compact microstrip filter-antenna meticulously crafted for operation within the 2.4 GHz ISM band and tailored to accommodate 4G applications. The compact design signifies a keen focus on portability and efficient space utilization—parameters paramount in the design of contemporary wireless devices. Simultaneously, the wide-band feature of the antenna signals a forward-looking approach, demonstrating an intention to meet the diverse frequency requirements inherent in 4G applications. This showcases the antenna's adaptability to the evolving landscape of communication standards. Noteworthy in its innovative approach, [13] introduces a departure from convention by integrating 3D printing and curvature into antenna design. This distinctive 3D printed curved monopole micro strip antenna is purpose-built for biomedical applications, underscoring the pursuit of inventive solutions in the health care sector. The integration of curvature and 3D printing techniques reflects a departure from traditional designs, suggesting an exploration of unconventional methodologies to potentially enhance antenna performance or meet specific requirements in the biomedical domain within the ISM band.

Figure 5:Electrical properties of pork tissue (a) permittivity 2.45GHzand (b)conductivityat2.45GHz

In synthesis, [10][11][12][13][14] collectively weave a rich tapestry of insights into the realm of mono pole antennas within the ISM band at 2.45 GHz. The literature review illuminates the

ongoing endeavors to optimize antenna performance for distinct applications, ranging from implantable biomedical devices to portable communication systems supporting standards such as GPS, ISM, W-LAN, and 4G. The thematic pursuit of versatility, compactness, and innovation emerges as a recurrent motif, highlighting the dynamic nature of antenna design in response to the evolving demands of wireless communication technologies.

Table 2: DIFFERENT TYPES OF ISM MONOPOLE ANTENNA WITH ITS DIMENSIONS:

REFERENCE	ANTENNA TYPE	ANTENNA SIZE (Lx W x H) (cu.mm)	DIELECTRIC CONSTANT	OPERATING FREQUENCY (G HZ)	ISM APPLICATIONS
[10]	Z-Monopole Antenna	7 x8 x0.65	9.8	F1=2.45	implantable medical devices.
[11]	M-Shape Printed Monopole Antenna	43.8 x18.6 x1.6	4.3	F1=2.4	GPS, ISM, and W-LAN applications
[12]	Microstrip Filter-Antenna	42 x45 x0.81	2.2 & 3.0	F1=1.57	2.4 GHz ISM Band and 4G wireless communication
				F2=2.4	
				F3=5.0	
				F4=5.8	
[13]	Curved Monopole Microstrip Antenna	71.5 x71.5 x2	-	F1=4.8	Biomedical Applications (Possibly for better integration with the human body)
				F2=8.6	

SECTION III: META MATERIALS

Metamaterials have emerged as a transformative avenue in antenna design, offering unprecedented possibilities to engineer electromagnetic properties. In the realm of Industrial, Scientific, and Medical (ISM) applications, researchers have explored the integration of metamaterial-inspired monopole antennas to address the escalating demand for versatile and efficient wireless communication systems. This literature review synthesizes insights from three key journals that delve into the intricacies of metamaterial monopole antennas tailored for ISM applications. [15] delves into the development of a dual-band antenna that seamlessly caters to ISM and Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) needs. By harnessing the unique properties of metamaterials, the antenna achieves enhanced radiation efficiency and expanded bandwidth. The inclusion of an Artificial Magnetic Conductor (AMC) backing serves as a pivotal innovation, directing and shaping the radiation pattern with precision. This dual-band

metamaterial antenna showcases the potential to concurrently support diverse applications within the ISM spectrum. In a parallel vein [16] illuminates the development of a novel antenna optimized for both Ultra-Wideband (UWB) and ISM frequencies. The antenna's design, inspired by metamaterial concepts, marks a leap towards the realization of multiband functionality crucial for contemporary wireless communication systems. A comprehensive characteristic mode analysis provides a deep understanding of the antenna's behaviour, unravelling valuable insights for further refinement. This research underscores the metamaterial's prowess in enabling antennas to seamlessly traverse diverse frequency bands within the ISM spectrum. Building on these foundations.[17] zeroes in on the challenges of crafting electrically small antennas for GSM and ISM frequency bands. Metamaterial structures take center stage in this design, allowing for the miniaturization of the antenna without compromising performance. In the intricate landscape of GSM and ISM applications, this metamaterial-inspired electrically small antenna stands as a testament to the feasibility of achieving optimal efficiency within confined spatial constraints. Collectively [15][16][17] unveil the potential of metamaterial monopole antennas as catalysts for innovation within the ISM spectrum. By leveraging the inherent advantages of metamaterials, these antennas not only address the current demands of ISM applications but also pave the way for future advancements in wireless communication systems, positioning themselves as pivotal components in the evolving landscape of modern technology.

SECTION IV: TEXTILE BASED ANTENNA

Wearable antennas designed for Industrial, Scientific, and Medical (ISM) band applications reveals a dynamic landscape marked by continuous innovation and a quest for optimal design. [18] contributes significantly to this discourse by delving into the practical aspects of seamlessly integrating antennas into textiles. In the realm of wearable technology, where comfort and flexibility are paramount, this study offers valuable insights into the delicate balance required for successful implementation. The exploration of the design process provides a nuanced understanding of how textile antennas navigate challenges such as bending and stretching, shedding light on the intricate interplay between functionality and user comfort.[19] extends the narrative by emphasizing the rigorous evaluation of wearable antennas tailored for ISM band use.

Figure 7: The Fabricated prototype of the proposed wearable antenna design

Figure 7: antenna placement on patients clothes

With a focus on key parameters like impedance matching, radiation pattern, and efficiency, this study provides a comprehensive analysis of the antenna's adaptability to diverse wearable scenarios. The significance of this research lies not only in the technical aspects but also in its exploration of how the antenna design addresses challenges posed by the proximity of the antenna to the human body. By scrutinizing real-world conditions, this journal enriches the literature with practical considerations, contributing to the ongoing conversation about achieving optimal performance in wearable technology.[20] introduces a sophisticated approach to antenna optimization. By integrating the CRO-SL algorithm into the design process, this study aims to enhance the performance and efficiency of planar textile antennas within the specific context of 2.4 GHz Wireless Body Area Networks (WBAN). The literature review reflects a broader trend in leveraging advanced optimization algorithms to fine-tune antenna parameters systematically. Understanding the role of algorithms like CRO-SL in elevating the overall effectiveness of wearable antenna designs is crucial for pushing the boundaries of performance in wireless communication systems. In summary, wearable antennas for ISM band applications is a tapestry woven with threads of innovation, practical considerations, and advanced optimization strategies. These journals collectively contribute to a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities in designing antennas for wearable technology, fostering a rich discourse that propels the field forward.

Figure 8: antenna measurement position

Figure9: The human body tissue model

Figure10: indoor testing of the antenna

3.CONCLUSION

This literature review reveals a dynamic landscape in the design of monopole antennas for ISM band applications. Researchers emphasize versatility and wideband performance, exploring innovative configurations like circular and Z-monopoles. The integration of metamaterials showcases transformative potential, enhancing radiation efficiency and enabling multiband functionality. Additionally, the exploration of textile antennas for wearables provides insights into balancing functionality with user comfort. These studies collectively contribute to the advancement of wireless communication technologies, offering valuable considerations for the engineering student's project. The significance lies in addressing challenges, meeting evolving standards, and designing compact, efficient antennas, underscoring the importance of continual innovation in the field.

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